

Impact of magnesium stearate and sodium starch glycolate on work of compaction, detachment and ejection stress of microcrystalline cellulose

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INTRODUCTION

Tablets account for 70% of all administrated pharmaceutical solid dosage forms and direct compression is most desirable manufacturing process based on low costs of production. However, excipients for direct compression should have specific physical properties like good flowability and high compressibility. Mechanical behavior of materials during compression is very important to be understated in order to obtain product of high quality. Deformation mechanism of materials during compression in literature is explained as plastic flow, brittle fracture and elastic recovery [1,2]. The most compressible excipient frequently used in industry include cellulose, lactose, polyols, starch and mineral salt. Microcrystalline cellulose is most common excipient for direct compression, however it is known that it has high elasticity which can reduce mechanical strength and give a rise to capping or lamination [3].

Understanding of behavior of excipients during compression is critical for development of high quality tablet formulation. In order to apply principles of quality by design (QbD) it is also very important to understand complex interactions of excipients used in formulations for direct compression and its resulting effect on tablet properties. Characterization of compaction process is important step in tablet formulation development. Better understanding of stress during ejection and detachment of tablets is essential for generation of large volume of data needed to support requirements of QbD,

AIM

The aim of the work was to determine the influence of magnesium stearate (MgSt) and sodium starch glycolate (NaSG) on work of compaction, ejection stress and detachment stress of MCC in placebo powder mixture for direct compression.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

In this research were used microcrystalline cellulose (Vivapur[®] 101, JRS Pharma, Germany), anhydrous lactose for direct compression (Supertab[®]21AN, DFE Pharma,

Germany), sodium starch glycolate (Primojel[®]), magnesium stearate (Magnesium stearate[®], Mosselman, Germany).

Method

Tabletability of material was determined using multifunctional Gamlen device (GTP-1). Tablets were produced at loads 250 and 500 kg. Sample size was 100 mg, tablet diameter was 6mm. From force-displacement curves were calculated work of compaction, ejection stress and detachment stress. Resistant to crushing of product tablets (Ph.Eur.9) was also measured. All measurements were done in triplicate. Pure MCC as well as placebo powder mixtures containing MCC, MgSt and NaSG were tested (two levels of concentrations of MgSt and NaSG, full factorial design was applied and total 4 powder mixtures were tested) (Table 1).

Formulation	MgSt	NaSG
F1	0,5%	1%
F2	1%	4%
F3	1%	1%
F4	0.5%	4%

Table 1. Formulation of placebo powder mixture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resistant to crushing of tablets at load 250 kg was lowest in F2 (110±0 N) and highest in F3 (141±1.5 N) (F1: 139±2.5 N, F4: 114±4.1 N, MCC: 130±5.2 N), and at load 500 kg was also lowest for F2 (178±1.5 N) and highest for F and F3 (237±3 N in both formulations) (F4: 182±7.7 N, MCC: 212±13 N). Thickness of tablets at load 250 kg was around 2.7 mm, and around 2.5 mm at load 500 kg in all tablet formulations.

Pure MCC has lower work of compaction than placebo powder mixture at both loads (Table 2). Addition of MgSt and Na SG leads to increase of energy needed for compaction. Lower concentration of NaSG contributes to higher work of compaction.

Figure 1: Elastic recovery (%), ejection stress (N*mm²) and detachment stress (N*mm²).

Formulation	load 250 kg	load 500 kg
MCC	1480.53±97.87	2293.29±23.92
F1	1774.78±9.84	2756.05±8.77
F2	1654.46±12.87	2483.48±10.90
F3	1745.96±13.46	2716.68±10.40
F4	1646±10.42	2509.39±29.66

Table 2. Work of compaction (N*m) for load of compression 250 kg and 500 kg

Increase in work of compaction imply that material absorbs more of energy during compaction which implies to elastic deformations. With addition of MgS and NaSG elasticity of MCC is improved [4].

Values of elastic recovery are highest for pure MCC, and significantly decrease with addition of MgS and NaSG.

Ejection stress up to 3 Nmm² should not lead to tablet problems [3]. From Figure 1 it is clear that pure MCC has high values of ejection stress and addition of both MgS and NaSG significantly decrease values. Detachment stress is also much higher for pure MCC in comparison to placebo powder mixtures.

CONCLUSION

It is clear from results that small amount of MgS and NaSG have high influence on compaction behavior of MCC. This approach of testing compaction behavior of formulations during small scale development phase would lead to better formulation selection and less problems during up-scale process.

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AGENDA

PAGE

POSTER SESSION ON WEDNESDAY, 12 MAY 2021

02

POSTER SESSION ON THURSDAY, 13 MAY 2021

08

POSTER SESSION ON FRIDAY, 14 MAY 2021

16

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POSTER SESSION ON WEDNESDAY, 12 MAY 2021

Cellular drug transport

Establishing an in vitro cornea model of Dry Eye Disease – wound healing and anti-inflammatory effects of serum on HCE-T cells

Isolation and characterization of porcine nasal epithelial cells for generation of novel immortalized cell lines with organotypic properties

Dermal preparations

Alkanediols as alternative preservatives for dermal formulations

Arabinoxylan and carboxymethyl cellulose composite blend films for antibiotic delivery to infected wounds

Assessment of antimicrobial and cytotoxic activity of *Eucalyptus globulus*

Bioactivity of *Echinacea purpurea* extracts, a putative cosmetic ingredient

Biosensors with and without carbon nanotube functionalization for monitoring skin pH and hydration in non-clinical settings: preliminary study

Characterization of topical formulations and skin penetration via confocal Raman microscopy

Cyclic siloxanes interact with human skin – evidence from spectroscopic, thermal and microscopic studies

Development and validation of HPLC method for determination of spironolactone in lamellar liquid crystal-based topical emulsions

Development of lipid nanoformulations for improved treatment of scalp psoriasis: a fluocionolone acetonide case study

Dissolving Microarray patches containing Artemether-Lumefantrine: Development, bioavailability and antimalarial studies in *Plasmodium yoelii*

Dressings as a protective barrier to prevent skin lesions in Healthcare Professionals during the COVID-19 pandemic: Tribological lubricant characterization

Encapsulation of Hesperetin Particles in an O/W Emulsion

Evaluation of the comparability of skin penetration analysis by confocal Raman microspectroscopy

Foamability and Foam Stability of Mono- and Diacylphosphatidylcholine Mixtures

Formulation and characterization of chitosan-based films as topical dressings

Influence of microemulsion and glycerol on minoxidil release from carrageen gel

Investigation of physiological skin parameters influenced by penetration enhancer methods

Methods to assess protein binding of drugs in the interstitial fluid

Monitoring of cytokines and eicosanoids in acute wounds

Multifunctional membranes based on β -glucans and chitosan useful in wounds treatment

Optimization of an 8% ciclopirox base and olamine-soluble polypseudorotaxanes nail lacquer for onychomycosis treatment.

Poly(lactic acid) electrospun fibers loaded with triterpene extract for wound dressing

Silk sericin: from textile waste material to dermatological and cosmetic applications

Study of acne patient adherence to topical and oral medication

The Biopolymer Bacterial Nanocellulose as a Platform for Nail Applications

The development of a hand-sanitizer preparation containing plant-based APIs

The influence of the preparation method to the moisturizing properties of a new hyaluronic gel

The spreadability and consistency of semisolid dermal formulation – correlation between extensometry and penetrometry

Topical acidification of the skin: contribution of alpha and beta hydroxy acids

Transformation/metamorphosis of topical film-forming systems upon application: contribution of tribological studies

Gene delivery

Glycogen-based cationic nanovectors for siRNA delivery to cancer cells

GMP-compliant sponge-like dressing containing MSC lyo-secretome: proteomic network of healing in a murine wound model

Lipid nanoparticles encapsulating miR199/204 to revert drug resistance in metastatic melanoma

Lipid-based nanocarriers for co-delivery of oligonucleotides and chemotherapeutics to glioblastoma

Modified β -cyclodextrin-based nanoparticles mediated delivery of siRNA for Huntingtin gene silencing

Polymeric Nanoparticles Based on Tyrosine-Modified, Low Molecular Weight Polyethylenimines for siRNA Delivery

Translating thin film rehydration method for cationic liposome manufacture to a microfluidics system for a liposomal pDNA vaccine against SARS-COV2

Green and sustainable pharma

Hydrolyzed keratin: a versatile excipient for pharmaceutical applications?

Nanoparticles and vesicles

A quality by design approach for liposomes production by innovative method using supercritical fluids: which parameters use to obtain good physicochemical characteristics?"

A mixture of non-ionic and cationic surfactants for the formulation of nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs)

API-loaded ApoA1-reconstituted high-density lipoprotein nanoparticles formulated by novel preparation technique

Biodynamers, pH-responsively degradable and fluorescent protein-like polymers for drug delivery

C. elegans as a model of type 2 diabetes to evaluate free and encapsulated quercetin

Characterisation of anionic and cationic amphiphilic cyclodextrins as novel materials for siRNA delivery

Characterization and evaluation of antibacterial activity of artemisinin and quinacrine loaded phospholipid vesicles

Cytotoxicity and cellular uptake of Cannabis sativa extract loaded nanostructured lipid carriers on hCMEC/D3 cells

Design of Dye and SPION loaded Lipid Nanocapsules for dual detectability

Design of solid powder particles for a needle-free injection

Design of STING ligand nanoparticles for improved cancer immunotherapy

Development and optimization of hydrogels loading PLGA-nanoparticle for wound healing

Development of a dissolution test method for nanoscale drug suspensions

Development of cargo-free nanostructured lipid carriers in alginate microspheres for colon cancer targeting and treatment

Development of molecularly imprinted nanoparticles for targeted delivery of betamethasone

Development of optimized protocols for the manufacturing of non-functionalized and functionalized poly(lactic-co-glycolic) acid nanoparticles

Development of PEGylated Solid Lipid Nanoparticles as Vectors for Gene Therapy

Development of Pravastatin Nanoparticles for Atherosclerosis Therapy

Differences in Cytokine Release of Human Leukocytes by Stimulation with different Toll-like Receptor Agonist loaded PLGA nanoparticles

Different serum, different corona! How reliable are in-vitro nanoparticle uptake experiments conducted in the presence of bovine serum?

Effects of penetration modifiers on in vitro skin permeation of idebenone from lipid nanoparticles

Effects of solid lipid and liquid lipid ratios on physical properties of stearylamine-containing nanostructured lipid carriers

Enhancing mitochondrial function using NO releasing nanoparticles; a potential approach for therapy of Alzheimer's disease

Evaluation of co-encapsulated fisetin and cisplatin into liposomes in vascularized tumor models

Evaluation of the biodistribution of PS- and PG-enriched liposomes and the impact of PEGylation by fluorescence imaging (FI)

Evaluation of the employment of INVITE nanomicelles in the prevention and maintenance therapy of diabetic retinopathy

Fusogenic liposomes for the delivery of ion channels into cell membranes; A potential platform for the treatment of channelopathies

How suitable is folic acid as targeting ligand in active targeting of breast cancer by nanocarriers?

Improvement of therapeutic efficacy of bicalutamide by incorporation into novel drug delivery systems

In vitro appraisal of polymeric nanoparticles designed for oral delivery of GLP-1 analog- Liraglutide

In vitro biocompatibility of transferosomes, ethosomes and transethosomes

In vivo efficacy of bevacizumab-loaded albumin nanoparticles in the treatment of colorectal cancer

Indocyanine Green based polymeric nanoparticles, an encouraging strategy for simultaneous cancer imaging and therapy

Influence of poly(vinyl alcohol) as emulsifier on the polymorphic behavior of tripalmitin nanoparticles

Loperamide loaded into poloxamer-coated nanocarriers: impact over solubility and intestinal cellular transport

LPS decoration on nanoparticles improves the outcome of cancer immunotherapy therewith

Modified polymeric nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery

Nanocarriers as a strategy to improve the anti-inflammatory activity of Sambucus nigra L. extract

Nanocrystal Manufacturing Using Controlled Expansion of Supercritical Solutions (CESS)

Nanoencapsulation of Buddleja globosa bioactive compounds in polymers derived from methacrylic acid

Nanoparticle in liposomes for the delivery of antimicrobials in multiple drug resistant bacteria

Natural polyglycerol ester-based low energy nanoemulsions prepared with specialty seed oils for dermal application

Oligomer-Stabilized Calcium Phosphate Nanoparticles for siRNA Delivery to Brain Tissue

Optimization of lipid nanoparticles formulation for nose-to-brain delivery using the quality by design (QbD) approach

Particle size distribution of cilostazol obtained by liquid antisolvent precipitation (LASP) and its combination with ultrasound

Pharmacokinetic and biodistribution studies of novel patent protected pyrazoloquinolinones formulated as nanosuspension

Polymeric nanoparticles as carriers for the delivery of pomegranate peels extract

Preparation and Characterization of Gemcitabine-ester loaded PLGA-nanoparticles

Preparation of superparamagnetic nanoemulsions by premix membrane emulsification

QbD development of long-circulating liposomes co-encapsulating Doxorubicin and Simvastatin for enhanced antitumor activity

Quality by Design-based development process for preparation of liposomal formulations

Quantitative AFM measurements reveal hidden changes in gelatin nanoparticles induced by preparation, and drug load

Reversal of liver fibrosis using collagenase loaded collagen binding nanoparticles; elucidation of the underlying toxicity

Role of Green Honokiol-loaded Transferosomes on a Key Player of The Tumor Microenvironment

Selective dissolution approach as analytical tool for individual particle size analysis of a drug combination nanosuspension

Self assemblies of azacitidine prodrugs : an innovative therapy against myelodysplastic syndromes

Self-assembled folate-targeted nanoparticles for dual-responsive release of Doxorubicin in cancer cells

Self-assembling nanoparticles: application of a thermo-responsive hyaluronic acid conjugate for osteoarthritis

Silk Fibroin Nanoparticle Functionalized with Arg-Gly-Asp cyclopentapeptide: Tumor-specific Active Targeting

Silk Fibroin Nanoparticles to Redirect Immunity Against Cancer

Solid lipid nanoparticles made of glycine and fatty alcohols for the minocycline nasal administration

Spray drying of API nanosuspensions: Important aspects for successful formulation and process development

Squalene-Near IR dye nanoassemblies targeting mitochondria with theranostic properties

Stacking as a Key Property for Creating Nanoparticles with Tunable Shape: the Case of Squalenoyl-Doxorubicin

Study of liposomes' uptake by the placental barrier using complementary in vitro and ex vivo models

Supercritical Fluid-Processed Liposomal Amphotericin B: Characterization and Pharmacokinetic study

Surface modification of nanostructured lipid carriers by maintaining particle size and hydrophobicity

Surface-modified curcumin nanocrystals

Sustainable Preparation Methods for the Encapsulation of Anti-inflammatory Small Molecules in Nanoparticles

The impact of serum source on the reliability of in-vitro nanoparticle-cell uptake experiments

TPGS polymeric micelles for poorly soluble drug delivery

Transfer of lipophilic drugs from nanoemulsions into lipid-containing alginate microspheres

Tumor penetrating gangliosilated liposomes to improve anticancer efficacy in cancer hypoxic area via M2 TAMs surface association

Ultrasound parameters for the determination of phospholipid transitions in liposomal dispersions

Visible-Light-Induced Click Chemistry for Nanoparticle Modification

Parenteral delivery

Dose adaption of TGF β 3 on implant for the reconstruction of tendon-to-bone junctions

Impact of oil phase selection on long-term stability and in vitro release of curcumin from PEGylated nanoemulsions

Manufacturing of Injectable Implants for Drug Delivery

PLGA-based in situ forming implants for controlled release of rilpivirine

Protein formulation and aggregation

Application of Stability Screening Tools for Protein Formulation Development

Can Polysorbate 20 Influence the Effect of Trehalose or Urea on a Monoclonal Antibody?

Development of the bacteriocin, lacticin 3147 from *Lactococcus lactis*, into an antibiotic

Excipient Combinations to reduce protein viscosity

Low-in-nanoparticulate-impurities sucrose for biopharmaceutical formulations

Mitochondrial calcium rise in thapsigargin-treated THP-1 monocytes is independent of NLRP3 inflammasome activation

Novel design of bioresponsive tri-functional peptide

Novel Developmental Surfactant for Improved Protein Stabilization

Optimization of IgG dry powder formulation stability based on polyol-sugar mixtures using a rational DoE

Photocrosslinked hydrogels: promising carriers for maintaining protein stability

Spray drying of monoclonal antibodies

Temperature-ramped molecular dynamics simulations to select aggregation-resistant antibodies

Towards a mechanistic understanding of bevacizumab stabilization with Hydroxypropyl β -Cyclodextrins

Quality assurance

Perception of Risk Among Pharmaceutical Stakeholders

Risk Assessment in Pharmaceutical Processes

Software Validation in the Pharmaceutical Industry

Understanding Risks in Pharmaceutical Processes

Quality control and PAT

A novel approach to determine the granule density of milled ribbons using multi-stage air classification combined with dynamic image analysis

Automated online process control and regulation in fluid bed granulation

Development and validation of uv-vis spectroscopic method of assay of carbamazepine orally disintegration tablets (ODT)

Development of a discriminating dissolution method for an ASD-based formulation using an AQbD approach

Does Magnesium Stearate influence the electrical charge of lactose powder?

Dynamic study of loss on drying in a continuous wet granulation process

HME process optimisation with in-line UV-Vis spectroscopy and machine learning algorithm

PAT monitoring of coating pan by nir: pls method calibration approach

Prediction of in vitro dissolution by Artificial Neural Networks and integrated modeling of continuous manufacturing

Quantification of Tablets Containing Multiple APIs Using Transmission Raman

Quantitative NMR for the determination of residual solvents in silica-based drug delivery systems

The Value of Pharmacopeial Reference Standards: Uncertainties, associated guard bands and secondary reference standards

Transdermal delivery

Advanced corneotherapy with lipid nanoparticles

Characterization, permeation, recovery, and histological study of a topical Keterolac-formulation across vaginal mucosa

Combination of Fentanyl with Antidote inTDS as an Anti-Abuse-Strategy - Misuse Simulation Methods for Fentanyl-TDS

Comparison Study of Skin Penetration Testing Methods

Curcumin encapsulation in protein-stabilized nanoemulsions for a topical application

Development and evaluation of azithromycin-loaded niosomes for transdermal delivery

Development of soft vesicular systems for dermal and transdermal delivery of non-psychoactive cannabinoids

Enhanced skin permeation of some drugs using ionic liquid based on the pharmaceutical additives

Ex Vivo Evaluation of Modulated Flavanones for the Intended Use in Topical Formulation

Hair follicle targeting with nanocrystals: influence of the vehicle on the penetration efficacy

Investigation of Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLC)-Based Gel for the Transdermal Delivery of Ibuprofen: Preparation, Characterization, Textural Properties and Ex Vivo Skin Permeation Studies

Monitoring drug penetration with PEGylated emulsifiers as penetration enhancers by confocal Raman spectroscopy

Silicone and polyacrylates as a matrix for transdermal delivery: influence of polymer type on drug diffusion

SmartFilms® as a novel transdermal drug delivery system

Structure and adhesiveness of various PSA-based DIA type transdermal delivery systems with indomethacin

Testing the efficacy of different penetration enhancers for dermal delivery of poorly soluble drugs – a case with sertaconazole nitrate

The influence of innovative versatile polymers in skin delivery: formulation of diclofenac sodium and permeation study

POSTER SESSION ON THURSDAY, 13 MAY 2021

Advanced drug delivery systems

- 3D Bioprinted Scaffolds for controlled release of Mesenchymal Stem/Stromal Lyo-secretome in Bone Regeneration
- 3D-Printing of paracetamol tablets by fused deposition modelling
- A comparative study of PLGA microparticles loaded with micro-sized and nano-sized dexamethasone
- A novel composite nanosystem as a potential tool for the local treatment of glioblastoma
- Aerosolized Nanoparticles for Nose to Brain Drug Delivery NTBDD
- Bioinspired contact lenses functionalized with cytosine for affinity-driven loading and release of transferulic acid
- Carbon Quantum Dots encapsulation in liposomes for lung delivery in Coronavirus infections
- Characterization of advanced Proticles – a new generation of drug delivery systems
- Characterization of printlets obtained from photoreactive dispersions by digital light processing (DLP) 3D technology
- Characterization of sonochemically prepared bovine serum albumin microcapsules using different plant oils as core component
- Chitosan and Chitosan-Lipid Hybrid Nanoparticles as Promising Carriers Relieve the Immune Suppressive Tumor Microenvironment in Triple Negative Breast Cancer
- Coating of Alginate Aerogel Particles in a Wurster Fluidized Bed for Drug Delivery
- Colon delivery of hydrophobic drugs by colloidal inulin cyclodextrin bioconjugates
- Comparison of PEGylated and non-PEGylated Proticles An in vitro and in vivo study
- Developing predictive models for optimising the properties of chitosan nanogels
- Development and Characterization of Mucoadhesive Films Containing Metronidazole for Vaginal Drug Delivery
- Development of a mucoadhesive, anhydrous and self-emulsifying vaginal base for compounded medications
- Development of liposomal formulations to increase the stability of cysteamine, a natural bioactive compound
- Erlotinib solubility measurements on aqueous and organic solutions: preliminary step towards new supersaturating delivery systems
- Eudragit® RL/RS-coated drug delivery systems based on shape memory poly(vinyl alcohol) for gastric or vesical retention
- Evaluation of methods to determine the encapsulation efficiency of curcumin in suspoemulsions
- Hot melt extrusion paired fused deposition modeling 3D printing techniques for fabrication of ketoprofen films for topical delivery
- Hyaluronic Acid Nanogel for Protein Delivery System
- Importance of combining particle size analysis techniques to characterize self-assemblies
- Improved In Vivo Photoprotective Activity of Ferulic Acid-loaded w/o/w multiple emulsions
- In vitro drug release of anthelmintic moxidectin-loaded lipid microparticles
- Lipid coated silica nanoclusters: nanocarriers for poorly soluble drugs
- Lipid nanocapsules loaded in alginate microcapsules for a pH-responsive controlled release system

Lipid nanoparticles for vaginal delivery of progesterone

Lipid nanoparticles with modified nanostructures

Local delivery of plant extracts by electrospun fibers for pharmacomicrobiomic treatment of periodontitis

Membrane interactions and uptake of an amphipathic cell- penetrating peptide, as a delivery system for miRNA

Microfluidic preparation of iRGD peptide functionalized solid lipid nanoparticles for targeted brain delivery

New dextran/polyethylenglycol-based cryogels for biomedical applications

New nanoparticle systems for co-delivery of paclitaxel and etoposide prodrug obtained using the nab-based technology

Nanofibrous proteolytic mats for wounds and burns sensitive debridement

Novel 3D Design Concept for the Development of Individualized Dosage Forms

Novel cellulose-based particles as an innovative, adsorptive carrier material for Solid-SNEDDS development

Ocular administration of Loteprednol Etabonate: Self-Assembling Nanomicelles to Improve Drug Ocular Efficacy

Physicochemical and biological characterization of electrospun fiber mats for the use as innovative substrates for 3D in vitro tissue models

Physicochemical characterization of oxidized cellulose sulfate based hydrogels

Polymer blends for hot melt extruded and injection molded controlled drug delivery systems

Polymorphic transitions in lipid microparticles loaded with the anthelmintic drug moxidectin

Preparation and Characterization of Vaginal Delivery of Voriconazole Loaded Mucoadhesive Organogels

Preparation by microfluidic technique of solid lipid nanoparticles as promising proteins brain deliver systems.

Rose-Bengal loaded transfersomes for melanoma treatment: in-vitro and ex-vivo evaluation

Satureja montana L. essential oils: chemical profiles/phytochemical screening and O/W NanoEmulsion antimicrobial activity

Selected aspects of orodispersible minitablets (ODMTs) preformulation

Self-assembling nanoparticles: a thermo-responsive hyaluronic acid conjugate as a drug delivery system for osteoarthritis

Square shaped microcontainers improve in situ colonic mucoadhesion and absorption of amoxicillin in rats

Systematic investigation of the influence of filament drug loading and tablet infill percentage on in vitro drug release from 3D printed dosage forms

Targeted nanobubbles as a theranostic tool to handle complement-mediated vascular thrombosis

Two-component perivascular drug delivery system for the prevention of vein graft failure

Advanced therapy medical products

Anticancer properties of novel phosphonate betulin derivatives for drug delivery system in breast cancer treatment

Cytotoxic activity of 3-O-diethoxyphosphoryl-28-O'-propynoylbetulin on human ovarian cancer cell line

Design and evaluation of short cationic amphiphilic peptides with selective anticancer activity

Emerging Treatments for Retinitis Pigmentosa

GMP validation of production process for freeze dried secretome from bone marrow mesenchymal stem/stromal cells

Induction of breast cancer cell death by an acetylenic derivative of betulin phosphate

Microparticulate poly(vinyl alcohol) hydrogel formulations for embedding and controlled release of polyethyleimine (PEI)-based nanoparticles

Silk fibroin/hyaluronic acid sponges that regulate the release of SDF-1a for tissue engineering

Technological Development of Freeze-dried Mesenchymal Stem Cell Secretome Formulations

Controlled drug delivery

3D printed PLGA implants loaded with ibuprofen – Proof of concept

A new biodegradable copolyester, poly(-caprolactone-co-butylene succinate), as matrix former for controlled release of drugs

An evaluation study of pharmacokinetics and anti-adhesion barrier efficacy of oxaliplatin-PLGA microparticle-loaded hydrogels for colorectal cancer treatment in Rats

An innovative combination of technological platforms screening for extended-release of a highly soluble drug

Clotrimazole-loaded sodium caseinate-poloxamer microparticles for oral candidiasis treatment

Co-processed starch/mannitol as a promising excipient for direct compression of controlled release tablets

Could antioxidant-liposomal gels improve the cochlear implant surgery?

Cross-linked potato starch matrix tablets for controlled drug delivery

Development and characterization of pharmaceutical filaments for 3D print of solid dosage forms

Development and optimization of hydrogels loading PLGA-nanoparticle for wound healing

Development of SR matrix tablet containing a new GPR40 agonist for first-in-human clinical trial

Dissolution Studies with 3D-printed Intravesical Inserts in Novel Biopharmaceutical Bladder Model

Doose Independent Drug release from 3D Printed Oral Dosage Forms

Drug loaded filament development for 3D printing dosage forms. Application of percolation theory

Drug micro carriers with a hyaluronic acid corona toward a diffusion limited aggregation within the vitreous body

Dry granulation vs direct compression: Formulation of PVA based sustained release tablets

Dynamic changes of the pH inside and outside PLGA implants prepared by HME

Effect of drug load in 3D printed systems with HPMC and metformine

Fabrication and Characterization of Budesonide Loaded pH and Time Dependent Nanofiber Drug Delivery Systems

Formulation and characterization of double-layered ranitidine-diclofenac sodium tablets for improved NSAID therapy

Formulation of core-shell microspheres for the delayed pulsed release of protein

Formulation of sustained release lipid-based matrix system for vaginal delivery using the tween-screw hot-melt extrusion method

How drug milling affects the key properties of cochlear implants loaded with dexamethasone and dexamethasone sodium phosphate

Impact of the HME manufacturing process on the burst release of ibuprofen from PLGA implants

Importance of the diameter of PLGA implants for system swelling and drug release

- Importance of the sampling procedure and drug loading for ibuprofen release from PLGA implants
- Improved Fluidised Bed Coating Scalability of Sustained Release Microparticles using the MicroCoat™ Technology
- Improved mechanical strength of floating tablets via in situ alginate crosslinking
- In situ forming oleogels as a long-acting depot formulation
- In Vitro Evaluation of Telmisartan Loaded PCL/Collagen Small Diameter Vascular Grafts
- In vitro modified-release of the cytotoxic agent, 4-[4,4-Diphenyl-4-(1-tricyclo[3.3.1.1^{3,7}]decyl)butyl]-1-methylpiperazine, from matrix tablets
- In vitro modified-release studies of 1-methyl-4-{3-[4-[α -(1-adamantyl)phenylmethyl]phenyl]propyl}piperazine matrix tablets
- In vitro modified-release studies on bupropion hydrochloride tablets using various Eudragit polymers
- In vitro modified-release studies on naltrexone hydrochloride from matrix tablets containing Eudragit® L100-55
- Iontophoresis vs. chemical penetration enhancers towards improved dermal drug delivery: A case study with curcumin
- Is PLGA 503H a potentially suitable matrix former for 3D printing of controlled release implants?
- Long-acting implantable dosage forms containing paliperidone palmitate obtained by 3D Printing
- Manufacturing of defined porous silica aggregates for the production of tailored dosage forms
- Mesoporous silica as a universal platform for continuous manufacturing of multi-API formulations
- Metformin chondroitin sulfate salt preparation and cytotoxicity evaluation
- Monitoring the distribution and release of dexamethasone and dexamethasone sodium phosphate within silicone matrices using Raman imaging
- PLGA implants for controlled dexamethasone delivery: Further insight into the drug release mechanisms
- Polymerized Ionic Liquids (PILs)-based Hydrogels as Innovative Drug Carriers in Controllable and Individualized Dosage Forms
- Printability of personalized 3D printed tablets: Influence of formulation and process parameters
- Programmable Drug Release from Prodrug Suspension
- Pulsatile release from high dose lipid press-coated tablet
- Release from PLGA matrices prepared by hot melt extrusion with different dexamethasone particle sizes
- Release Profiles of Coated Matrix Tablets Developed Under Quality by Design (QbD) Methodology
- Rheological and mucoadhesive properties of vegetable extract with potential use in pharmaceuticals as controlled release and bio-adhesive excipient in inflammatory bowel disease.
- Rheology of ibuprofen - PLGA blends
- Robustness of drug release from cross-linked potato starch-based controlled release tablets
- Screening of pharmaceutical polymers for FDM 3D printing of patient-tailored tablets
- Silicone matrices for controlled drug delivery to the inner ear: Combining dexamethasone and dexamethasone sodium phosphate
- Study of novel chitosan-based hydrogel as drug carrier for antifungal drug caspofungin acetate.
- Sustained release matrix tablets based on starches: Impact of the starch nature and chemical modifications
- Synthesis of a Redox-Responsive Blend of Polymers and Application to the Nanoencapsulation of Retinol

The effects of polymethacrylate polymers as carriers on the release of simvastatin from SMEDDS-based drug delivery systems
Thiamine-poly(anhydride) coated zein nanoparticles for in vivo delivery of oral insulin
Ultrasound-induced release of Rhodamin B from polylactic acid nanoparticles
Xanthan–mannitol, a new directly compressible co-processed excipient for controlled release of melatonin

Oral delivery

3D powder bed printing of lactose tablets
3D printed capsules for colon targeted drug delivery
3D Printed Microdevices for Oral Drug Delivery
3D printing of abuse-deterrent and alcohol resistant formulations with modified release properties
A customized screening tool approach for the development of a self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS)
A novel carrier for the formulation of amorphous solid dispersion and solubility enhancement of poor water soluble drugs
A systematic approach for assessing the applicability of different types of nasogastric and PEG tubes for the administration of coated pellet formulations
Advantages of Using a Directly Compressible Starch in the Formulation and Scale-up of Ibuprofen Tablets
Application of Artificial Intelligence to Drug Product Development: a Quality-by-Design case study
Application of NUTRIOSE® FB06D, a soluble dextrin, as dry binder in tablets prepared by direct compression
Cellulose nanocrystals: A potential hydrogel drug carrier and nanocomposite for reinforcement of hot melt extrudates
Cochleate nanoparticles for the oral administration of Amphotericin B for leishmaniasis treatment
Compaction Analysis Simplified with the Gamlen Dashboard Software
Compaction behavior of freeze-dried trehalose
Comparison of In Vitro Lipolysis of Bosentan-Loaded Lipid Based Formulations in Fasted State Biorelevant Media
Comparison of the compaction properties of granulated and spray-dried lactose with and without a disintegrant
Compression Profiles of a Directly Compressible Starch using Compaction Simulation and High-Speed Tablet Press
Conversion of Liquid Pharmaceutical Formulations to Powders by using Syloid® XDP Mesoporous Silica Gel
Development and Evaluation of Ready-to-Use Hot Melt Coating / Formulations for Taste Masking
Development and In Vitro Characterization of Bosentan-Loaded Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System
Development of structured orodispersible film templates for the improved drug loading in inkjet printing
Direct compression of probiotics: A screening study
Direct cyclodextrin based powder extrusion 3D printing for one-step production of BCS Class II drug loaded tablets
Effect of lipid composition of SLN on oral permeability of a new BCS class IV drug: Witepsol® versus Gelucire®
Effect of Simulated Intestinal Media Composition on Solubility and Permeability of Cinnarizin, Dipyridamole and Fenofibrate
Emulsification speed of amphiphilic starches

Encapsulation method for oral delivery of a complex mixture of microorganisms

Enhanced Loading Efficiency and Mucoadhesion Properties of Gellan Gum Thin Films by Complexation with Hydroxypropyl- β -Cyclodextrin

EVA as a matrix excipient for personalized 3D printed tablets using HME and FDM

Evaluation of Partially Pregelatinized Starch in a Continuous High Shear Wet Granulation Process

Exploratory study of Aripiprazole-Adipic acid Cocrystals produced by Hot Melt Extrusion Techniques for improved Solubility and Dissolution rate

Fabrication of ondansetron 3D printed orally disintegrating printlets (ODP) via selective laser sintering

Flow Properties, Morphology and Compression Characteristics of a Directly Compressible Starch Before and After Feeding through Loss in Weight Continuous Feeder

Formulation and characterization of tablets with dry birch leaves extract

Formulation of essential oil tablets through microencapsulation and subsequent compression

Formulation of orodispersible carbamazepine/hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin tablets with five-in-one high functionality excipients for direct compression

Formulation of tablets containing mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with pramipexole

Furosemide: In vitro modified-release studies from ulvan tablets

How do Orodispersible Tablets Behave in an In Vitro Oral Cavity Model

Impact of glycerol on the coil/helix transition of gelatin and the viscoelastic behavior of soft capsule shell formulations

Impact of phospholipids on Prediction of Solubility Limited Fraction Absorbed in Physiologically Based Biopharmaceutics Modelling

Impact of Surface Properties of Core Material on the Stability of Hot Melt Coated Multiparticulate Systems

Improving treatment in maple syrup urine disease patients with personalized isoleucine printlets (3D printed tablets)

In vitro models of the intestinal mucosa for testing anti-inflammatory nanomedicine

In vitro Permeability Comparison of HPC-based Itraconazole Nanosuspensions

Influence of anaesthesia and capsule size in the gastric emptying of non-disintegrating capsules in rats

Influence of binder critical material attributes of hydroxypropyl cellulose in high-shear mixing

Influence of the cooling regime on the gel elasticity of soft gelatin capsule shell formulations

In-use Stability Improvement of the Moisture Sensitive Drug Ranitidine HCl Through Excipient Selection
In-use Stability Improvement of the Moisture Sensitive Drug Ranitidine HCl Through Excipient Selection

Investigation of the Impact of Formulation and Processing Conditions on Drug Release from An Aqueous Ethylcellulose Dispersion

MicroCoatTM for the development of Sustained Release Fixed Dose Combination Products in Microparticle-Filled Straw for Patients with Dysphagia

Microcontainers protect the prodrug valaciclovir from degradation in the intestinal environment

Mitigation of Sensitive API Degradation through Lipid-based Formulation and Soft Gelatin Capsule

Mucus-permeating nanocarriers for oral delivery of insulin. From in vitro to in vivo

Novel approach to treat genotype-specific hypertension using a riboflavin/amlodipine polypill

Novel authentication technology using molecular tags as a PCID in solid oral dosage forms

Oral administration of Dalargin: Improvement of peptide stability by cyclodextrin grafted ammonium chitosan

Pharmaceutical development of an orally disintegrating tablets of carbamazepine using the SeDeM diagram tool

Physico-chemical alterations of saliva caused by radiation therapy in head and neck area

Polymeric-based nanocarriers: a study of their mucus permeating properties

Preparation of multiple-unit tablets containing enteric-coated pellets with diclofenac sodium using novel calcium-phosphate-based starter pellets

Production of Different Nanoemulsions with High Energy Method for Oral Drug Delivery

Scaled-up production and tableting of grindable electrospun fibers containing an oral antisense oligonucleotide

Scaled-up solid formulation of living anaerobic bacteria for oral delivery using electrospinning

Stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing of an antihypertensive polyprintlet: Case study of an unexpected photopolymer-drug reaction

Study of Formulation and Manufacturing of Fixed dose Combination ER and Glipizide IR Bilayer Tablets

Tablet formulation studies with co-processed excipients for direct compression

The influence of filament composition on the properties of 3D printed tablets with bicalutamide

Understanding the Physical Chemistry of the Buffering Action by Bicarbonate: Prospects in Enteric-Coated Dosage Form Development

Use of pea starch maltodextrins in nutraceutical formulations

Pediatric and geriatric drug delivery

3D printed orodispersible films loaded with a thermosensitive and bitter drug substance

Acceptability of a sublingual drug formulation for respiratory tract infections in children aged 3 to 5 years

Adherence and acceptability of an oral antibiotic used for the prevention of pediatric urinary tract infection in Japan

Characterization of micro-extrusion 3D printing for the production of dose homogeneous paediatrics orodispersibles PrintletsTM

Development of Compartmental Films for Simplified Administration

Development of orodispersible films as dosage forms for pediatric patients

Extrudate materials via hot melt extrusion mask the bitter taste of drugs used for neglected tropical diseases

Fixed-Dose Combination coated mini-tablets designed for the management of GERD in paediatric patients

Hydroxypropyl-beta-cyclodextrin as a multifunctional excipient in orodispersible films

Rapid Dissolving Capsules for the Administration of Enteric Coated Prednisolone Microparticles

Review of methods for TPMT biomarker genotyping in the personalisation of thiopurine therapy

Safety and Efficacy characteristics of pharmacists recommended medications for paediatric patients

Technological approaches for extemporaneous preparation of oral pediatric formulations with sildenafil citrate

Regulatory affairs

A National System for Medical Device Incident Reporting

Defining a strategy for successful compliance to the new Medical Device Regulation

Drug utilization research on medication adherence: a case of fixed versus free combination of antihypertensive drugs

Facilitating patient access to quality medicines: Associations between USP Monograph Standards, ANDA Approval and Prescription Drug Costs

Medical Devices Directive in the European Union adapting to the EU Regulations

Medicinal substances meet medical devices: Drug-Device Combinations and their neighbours

Perception of Rare Diseases and Orphan Medicines

Perspectives in quality control of cannabis for medicinal purposes

Regulatory Science Research in Pharmacovigilance - The Experience of the Malta Medicines Authority

The impact of the pharmaceutical legislation on market penetration of biosimilar drugs: a drug utilization study

Technical Innovations

A new method to produce high-dose loaded dissolving microarray patches

Gentle Drying for Probiotic Products

Inhibition of bacterial biofilm formation in biomedical device after poly(methylmethacrylate)-co-dimethylacrylamide plus silver nanoparticles coating

Simultaneous estimation of naltrexone and bupropion hydrochloride in a binary mixture using UV spectrophotometry

The ISOLPHARM project: proof of concept of no-carrier added radioisotopes production and development of innovative radioconjugate for cancer therapy

Track-and-Trace: Novel Anti-Counterfeit Measures using Combined 2D-3D Printing Technologies

Veterinary

In-vitro evaluation of organogel based systems for veterinary use

Production, characterization, and in vitro efficacy of canine and equine lyo-secretome injectable formulation in regenerative medicine

POSTER SESSION ON FRIDAY, 14 MAY 2021

Bioavailability and absorption enhancement

Absorption profile of oleocanthal in rats

Amorphous solid dispersions of cannabidiol with an increase of the aqueous solubility: influence of the carrier, the hot melt extrusion parameters and the use of a crystallization inhibitor

Correlation of experimentally determined lipophilicity with in silico blood-brain permeation of new succinimide derivatives

Development of prednisolone containing in situ gelling ophthalmic formulations

Effect of 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin on the solubility and permeability of psoralen and 5-methoxypsoralen

Effect of carrier type and surfactant concentration on the silymarin release

Evaluation of potential of amino acids for amorphization and dissolution improvement of carvedilol

Exploring NSAIDs bioavailability through THEDES-like liquid formulations

Fraction of Drug Absorbed Predicted from In Vitro Flux Measurements

Impact of mucoadhesive polymeric nanoparticles containing thermosensitive hydrogels on transcorneal administration of 5-fluorouracil

Improvement of fenofibrate aqueous solubility by using mesoporous silica impregnation under pressurized carbon dioxide

Improving the bioavailability of anti-tuberculosis drugs through deep eutectic systems

Influence of pharmaceutical polymers on the recrystallization and dissolution of nimodipine

Influence of the luminal perfusion rate in the determination of the effective intestinal permeability coefficient of levofloxacin

Marinosolv: A novel solubilization technology

Mesoporous silica: a solution for amorphous stabilization of poor glass formers

Microenvironmental pH-modified solid dispersions for improving dissolution rate of valsartan

Microwave-induced in situ amorphization: mechanistic studies and application in indomethacin solid dispersion

Novel biphasic lipolysis testing of nilotinib lipid based suspensions to predict in vivo performance

Permeability and biocompatibility evaluation of olopatadine hydrochloride viscous ophthalmic solutions using in vitro 3D corneal model

Predicting the performance of amorphous solid dispersions

Semi-volatile solvent mixtures: a novel approach to liquid systems preparation

Solid lipid nanocarriers to increase oral bioavailability of the peptide Leuprolide

Spray drying of amorphous solid dispersions (ASD): small scale screening of batches containing less than 50 mg API

Structural Dynamics and Diffusion in Solid Dispersions

Synthesis of Novel Esters of Ciprofloxacin as Prodrugs for Improved Activity

Synthesis, physicochemical, biopharmaceutical and antimicrobial characterisation of Gatifloxacin n-butanoate, Gatifloxacin iso-butanoate and their ionic liquid salts as prodrugs for ocular drug delivery

Buccal and nasal delivery

Application of a Thermosensitive In Situ Gel of Chitosan-Based Nasal Spray Loaded with Tranexamic Acid for Localised Treatment of Nasal Wounds

Cytokine mediated inflammation in the oral cavity: Consequences on drug delivery

Design of Dextran Sulfate/Poly-L-lysine Nanogel for Ovalbumin delivery

Development of matrix for freeze-dried buccal vaccines

Development of mucoadhesive carrier systems for flavoring agents

Drug delivery strategies of Geraniol via nose-to-brain for the treatment of neuronal disorders

Formulation of *Cardiospermum halicacabum* extract loaded vesicles for nasal delivery.

In vitro release methodologies for nasal powder testing

Orodispersible films: A delivery platform for solid lipid nanoparticles?

Self-assembly multilayer films for buccal drug delivery: the impact of polymer cross-linking

Soluble Idebenone/Hydroxypropyl- β -Cyclodextrin Inclusion Complex for nasal administration

In vivo - in vitro correlations

A microfluidic human cornea model with dynamic dilution profile for in vitro drug absorption studies

Cryopreservation using Natural Deep Eutectic Systems: A new tool for pharmaceutical applications

Development of in vitro methods to evaluate the bitter taste using extra-oral bitter receptors

Direct visualizing of immediate release tablet disintegration; in vivo and in vitro studies

Formulation development of Telmisartan driven by flux measurements

In quest of a suitable tool to assess drug and nanomedicine penetration into tumor spheroids

Towards enabling IVIVC for orally inhaled products: PBPK modelling in dry powder inhaler development

Usefulness of small scale biphasic dissolution experiments in estimating precipitation rates for input in PBPK modelling

Pharmaceutical manufacturing and engineering

3D nanofibrous scaffolds for tendon reconstruction

3D printing of personalized bioresorbable airway stents

3D Printing of tablets via fused deposition modeling - Focus on filament production

3D-printing of suppositories based on hard fat

A mixture design approach to optimizing spray-dried sericin-based formulations

An existing polymer reinvented: A new particle designed polyvinyl alcohol for coating applications

Analysis and optimization of a pharmaceutical production process by computer simulation

Applying optical coherence tomography during film coating development

- Cellulosic dry binders in direct compression and roll compaction: effect of particle size and mechanical properties on tablet performance
- Characterization and modeling of the viscoelasticity of pharmaceutical tablets
- Characterizing powders flowability and triboelectric behavior for continuous manufacturing applications
- Comparison of artificial neural networks and response surface methodology for efficient extraction of rosmarinic acid from *Satureja kitaibelii*
- Comparison of the robustness of pellet film coating with and without in-process coating thickness evaluation
- Continuous small batch OSD production @ 9σ level
- Correlation study between SeDeM diagram expert system tool and the rotary press simulator Styl'ONE applied to a Zidovudine's direct compression industrial tablets formulation.
- Developing a framework to acquire the Rp-distribution of a spin-freeze dried product
- Development of a spray dried enteric release form of essential oil prepared by co-spray drying polysaccharides and methacrylate.
- Development of flow cell for in-situ visualization of dissolution processes in solid dosage forms
- Direct compression of QESD crystallized metformin hydrochloride into high-drug-loaded tablets
- Directly compressible spray dried powders obtained by dry coating using pharmaceutical mills
- DoE Combined with Process Automation: a New Approach to Quality by Design
- Does Tableability Really Improve With Decreased Diameters of Tablet Punches?
- Downstream processing of co-amorphous olanzapine
- Effect of binder type and lubrication method on the binder efficacy for direct compression
- Effect of dry ball milling process on curcumin crystals and its impact on physico-chemical and biopharmaceutical properties
- Effect of exposure time on dimensional accuracy and dissolution rate of printlets fabricated with DLP 3D printer
- Elastic properties of various Lactose grades during compaction, evaluated by ultrasonic-measurement system KIM
- Enhancement of nifedipine solubility in supercritical carbon dioxide: role of co-solvents
- Estimation of material hold-up in twin-screw granulation
- Evaluation of dry granulation and tableting for a formulation with a high amount of herbal drug using Design of Experiment
- Evaluation of hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC) for aqueous-based film coating system
- Fluidized and Spouted Bed for the preparation of directly processable amorphous solid dispersions
- Formation of delta-mannitol by co-spray drying to enhance tableability of paracetamol-mannitol formulations
- Formulation and Characterization of Dissolvable PLGA-Loaded Microneedles for Ocular Drug Delivery
- Formulation by design (FbD) applied for the identification of Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) in process manufacturing of chitosan/glycosaminoglycan electrospun scaffolds
- Formulation of Microorganisms to Tablets: How Different Process Steps Influence the Microbial Viability
- How to improve dies loading when using poor flowable powders
- Impact of incorporated APIs on material properties of hot-melt extruded amorphous solid dispersions

- Impact of magnesium stearate and sodium starch glycolate on work of compaction, detachment and ejection stress of microcrystalline cellulose
- Induced Jet Decay from Flow-Channel Streams
- Influence of binder attributes on binder effectiveness in a continuous twin screw wet granulation process via wet and dry binder addition
- Influence of degree of disorder on the inter-particulate bonding of lactose particles
- Influence of Mesoporous Silica (MPS) on Flow and Tribo-electrostatic Charging during Manufacturing
- Influence of Residence Time in Manufacturing Amorphous Solid Dispersions via Hot Melt Extrusion
- Inline Characterization of Dispersive Mixing Properties in Twin Screw Extrusion
- Investigation of a Model for Mixing Capacity in a Rotary Tablet Press
- Investigation of different mannitol grades and their performance on a dosing-disc capsule filling machine
- Investigation of the Dissolution Behavior of APIs for the Description of Inherent Solubility Properties
- Investigation on the dustiness of a binary powder mixture with a newly developed two-chamber setup
- Linking raw material characteristics and process settings to granule CQAs in continuous twin screw granulation
- Liquid Carbon Dioxide for the Production of Small Droplets
- Liquisolid systems with mesoporous silica based carriers: An investigation of flow and compaction properties
- Manufacture of amorphous solid dispersions by spray drying using a coaxial three-fluid nozzle
- Medications with novel 3D printed tactile patterns for patients with visual impairment
- Microfluidics and pharmaceutical devices by 3D printing
- Mind the Gap – Importance of Particle Distance During Drying of API-Nanosuspensions in a Fluidized Bed Process
- Next Generation Lipid-Based Excipients: Development of dry powders for inhalation via spray drying
- NIR spectroscopy as real time control tool for tablets manufacturing
- Optimization of processing times and temperature for 3D-printing of tablets
- Particle agglomeration analysis using PATVIS APA and deep learning
- Performance of anhydrous lactose in roller compaction
- PLGA nanoparticles manufacturing : comparison of ultrasound based production method
- Powder vs. granules – material characterization of binary powder blends and roller compacted granules for oral solid dosage forms
- Prediction of tablet weight variability based on process parameters and blend properties
- Preparation and characterization of electrospun polycaprolactone (PCL) tubular scaffolds for bioengineering of small-diameter blood vessels
- Preparation of Submicron Particles via Spray Drying using Ultrasonic Nebulization and Electrostatic Precipitation
- Printability of paracetamol-PCL filaments in FDM 3D process
- Processability of poly(vinyl alcohol) filaments prepared by hot melt extrusion for fused deposition modelling 3D printing
- Production and characterization of Polydioxanone (PDO) fibers by centrifugal spinning for biomedical application

Production of Drug Nanocrystals Engineered using a High Throughput Microfluidic Reactor

Raman Microscopy of Low-dose Filaments For 3D Printing

Rational design of solvent-based ASD production processes

Spray Drying versus Freeze Drying of cytokines exemplified by the model protein CXCL8

Spray Flash Evaporation and its extension for the submicronization of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients

Synthesis physicochemical and biopharmaceutical characterization of trimethoxybenzenesulfonamide (TMBS)- a new derivative of gallic acid

Tabletability of Oil-loaded Powders

Tackling ASD Flowability: Optimization in Downstream Processing

Tacrolimus suppositories prepared by semisolid-extrusion 3D printing for the treatment of Inflammatory Bowel Disease

The effect of lactose particle size on the tablet strength - compaction pressure relationship

The impact of suction pressure on die filling on rotary presses

The influence of lower punch vibration on the compactability and bondability of different types of microcrystalline cellulose

The role of online content uniformity measurement in the rapid automated process development of a continuous production system used for direct-filling hard gelatin capsules

Twin-screw granulation: An attempt for a quantitative description of screw configuration impact

Using microfluidics for the development of chitosan nanogels for gene therapy

Physical pharmacy

3D printed capsules for modulating the sustained release rate from a nanocellulose hydrogel

Dissolution in Intestinal Bicarbonate Buffer: Mass Transport-Dependent Effective pKa and its Implications

Enantiomeric amino acids as co-amorphous systems

Evaluation of Phase Transition of Bicalutamide in Tablets Under Different Storage Conditions

FDM 3D printing of flexible materials for pharmaceutical dosage forms

How Does the Content of Kollidon®VA64 Inhibit the Recrystallization and Improve Dissolution of Ezetimibe from Amorphous Solid Dispersions?

Polymorphism and drug release modification of tristearin-based formulation: the effect of liquid additives

Relationship between particle size and adhesion forces in Neusilin® US2 particles

Solid state amorphization of riboflavin upon milling

Solid state conversion of olanzapine during tableting

Thermal treatment to stabilize/destabilize pharmaceutical glasses

Toward biopredictive dissolution conditions for ionizable BCS class II compounds

Viscosity of ASDs at humid conditions

Preformulation

Assessment of side effects of SMEDDS in the rat

Combination of itraconazole cocrystal and nanocrystal techniques to improve the saturation solubility and dissolution rate

Effect of Maillard reaction on electrospun scaffolds for skin tissue engineering

Electrospun scaffolds in periodontal wound healing

Evaluation of Compressibility Index by SeDeM system method to predict the behavior of some tablets excipients

Evaluation of nephelometric high-throughput method in drug formulation development

Griseofulvin (BCS Class II Drug) Solubilization by Beta Cyclodextrin Derivatives Complexation

Hydrates as a water source for microwave induced in situ amorphization of celecoxib

Hydroxypropyl β Cyclodextrin as a High Efficiency Cholecalciferol Solubilizer

Insights from the preclinical development of Corallopyronin A: Establishing analytical assays for the determination of Corallopyronin A, Corallopyronin isomers and degradation products of stability and bioanalytical samples.

Insights from the preclinical development of Corallopyronin A: Formulation evaluations by physiology-based pharmacokinetics and in vivo predictive in vitro tools

Liquid marbles for bioavailability enhancement of poorly soluble drugs – a case study

Multivariate analysis of powder flow parameters to improve the development of blends for direct compression

Next Generation Lipid-Based Excipients: Solid State - Stability Relationship

Optimization of Bicalutamide-loaded 3D-printing Filament Composition

Oral liquid formulations of carvedilol in medium-chain triglycerides for use in paediatrics

Predicting powder flowability utilizing material characteristics and multivariate approach

Preparation, thermal analysis and phase solubility study of Quercetin inclusion complexes with β -cyclodextrin derivatives

Smart UV: An evolving strategy in sunscreen protection

Studies on modifications of established silk fibroin production methods to enhance protein content

Towards biocompatible formulations of steroids: Preparation of zuranolone nanoformulations

Pulmonary delivery

Activity evaluation of supramolecular compound based on N-acetylcysteine for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* biofilm

Comparing the mechanical properties of Quali-V®-I and Quali-V®-I Extra Dry capsules for use in dry powder inhalers

Effect of lumen enlargement on functionality of halloysite-chitosan sustained-release nanocontainers

Evaluation of pulmonary and renal tolerance of a cisplatin-based dry powder for inhalation to treat lung cancer

How important is internal lubricant in capsules for inhalation?

Hybrid lipid/polymer nanoparticles for pulmonary delivery of siRNA in cystic fibrosis lung inflammation

In vitro / in vivo Correlation of Two Commercial pMDI Formulations using NGI Analysis with 3D Printed Modified Induction Ports

In vitro Aerodynamic Assessment and Dissolution Profile of Spray-dried Itraconazole Powders for Inhalation from Aqueous Nanosuspensions

In vitro-in silico approach in the assessment of drug deposition and absorption following intratracheal insufflation of an ordered mixture in rats

Novel inhalable redox responsive nanoparticles for the combined treatment of lung cancer

Optimal Carrier Properties For Vaporizing Cannabinoids

Physicochemical factors affecting development of Vancomycin delivery in high dose DPI formulations

Synthesis of rifampicin and pyrazinoic acid biodegradable nanoconjugates for pulmonary delivery

The impact of interaction between inhaled drugs and lung surfactant on in-vitro solubility and predicted in-vivo performance

Stability testing

Cocoa butter and its stability in extemporaneous semisolid formulations

Determination of antioxidant effect of polyols in a cell free environment

DMTA test as an effective rheological alternative for accelerated freeze-thaw stability testing of O/W emulsions

Exploring the Performance and Stability-Controlling Tablet Disintegration Mechanisms

Influence of drug load on the stability of phospholipid-stabilized lipid nanoemulsions

Overcoming The Color Stability Issue Exhibited By Indigo Carmine In Film Coating Formulations

Starting materials

Enzymatically synthesized nanocellulose for drug delivery

GRANFILLER-D® As a New Co-processed Excipient For Orally Disintegrating Tablets Produced by Direct Compression

Pharmaceutical powder tribo-charging: the impact of relative humidity and twin-screw feeding

When CDs Meet DCs: Amphiphilic Cyclodextrin Particles Induce Potent Immune Responses

Chairs and committees

Chair of the conference

Eva Roblegg, University of Vienna/University of Graz, Austria

Co-chairs of the conference

Jörg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

Anna Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari, Italy

Jürgen Siepmann, University of Lille, France

Chair of the programme committee

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Programme

Tuesday, 11 May 2021

13:00 – 13:45	Opening Ceremony	Exhibition
13:45 – 14:45	Key note lecture	
14:45 – 15:15	Coffee break	
15:15 – 17:45	Hot topic lectures	

time zone
CEST

Key note lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Duncan Craig, University College London

- 13:45 - Engineering cancer immunotherapy
14:45 David J. Mooney, Harvard School of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Cambridge, USA

14:45 - 15:15 Coffee break/exhibition

Hot topic session incl. Q&A

Chairs: Svetlana Ibric, University of Belgrade and Maïke Windbergs, University of Frankfurt

- 15:15 - Digital assistant to support drug product development
16:00 Ferdinand Brandl, BASF, Ludwigshafen, German
- 16:05 - Overcoming challenges of biodegradable drug delivery systems
16:50 Steven Schwendeman, Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences and the Biointerfaces Institute, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, USA
- 16:55 - Pfizer's „continuous“ journey - Implementing continuous manufacturing into a factory for solid dosage forms
17:45 Clemens Stief, Pfizer, Freiburg, Germany

Wednesday, 12 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session			
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch			
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: Advanced therapeutic products incl. Q&A

Chairs: Karine Andrieux, University Prais Sud and Andreas Zimmer, University of Graz

- 08:45 - Formulation approaches for cell and gene therapies
09:30 Chris Van der Walle, GlaxoSmithKline, Stevenage, United Kingdom
- 09:35 - Comparison of different chromatography-based purification strategies for AAV vectors
09:50 Ruth Rieser, University of Munich, Germany

- 09:50 - Formulation of cationic liposomes enhances the immunogenicity of pDNA vaccine against SARS-COV-2
10:05 Allegra Peletta, ISPSO, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Biodrugs and advanced therapy medicinal products: a revolution in medicine
11:10 Maria Luisa Nolli, NCNbio, Milan, Italy

Invited talks: Solid dosage forms incl. Q&A

Chairs: Iris Ziegler, Cordon Pharma and Raphael Wiedey, University of Düsseldorf

- 08:45 - Adoption of the MCS concept in the pharmaceutical industry
09:30 Michael Leane, Bristol-Myers Squibb, New York City, USA/Kendal Pitt, GlaxoSmithKline, Ware, UK
- 09:35 - Process design for innovative drug delivery systems
10:20 Jukka Rantanen, Department of Pharmacy, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- 10:25 - The importance of understanding the physical and chemical properties of APIs in the digital design of drug products
11:10 Kevin Roberts, Faculty of Engineering, University of Leeds, United Kingdom

Short talks: Controlled drug delivery

Chairs: Werner Weitschies, University of Greifswald and Julijana Kristl, University of Ljubljana

- 08:45 - Design and control of a floating gastroretentive drug delivery system made by hot-melt tube extrusion
09:00 Paul Bebernik, University of Bonn, Germany
- 09:00 - A new calcium oral-controlled-release system based on zeolite for prevention of osteoporosis
09:15 Anna Maria Piras, University of Pisa, Italy
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Spray dried microparticulate drug delivery systems for long-term local osteoarthritis treatment
09:50 Carlota Salgado, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 09:50 - Tuning the mechanical poreproperties and release profile on an antimicrobial peptide from an injectable hydrogel using glycol chitosan
10:05 James Flynn, University of Limerick, Ireland
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - Development of N-acetylcysteine-functionalized microcontainers for degradation of biofilm matrix
10:40 Stine Egebro Birk, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark
- 10:40 - SymBiosys® based long acting injectable miroparticle formulations for large proteins
10:55 Tanja Henzler, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany

Programme

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Short talks: Preformulation and bioavailability

Chairs: Catherine Herry, NextPharma and Lea Ann Dailey, University of Vienna

08:45 - In situ drug amorphization using laser irradiation
09:00 Nele-Johanna Hempel, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

09:00 - Understanding the Release of ITZ:HPMCAS
09:15 Amorphous Solid Dispersions
Patrícia Nunes, Hovione, Portugal

09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30

09:35 - Evaluation of different preprocessing methods of
09:50 x-ray micro computed tomography images
Sebastian Bollmann, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

09:50 - Experimental and numerical studies of input
10:05 parameters calibration for the simulation of the
wet granulation process for pharmaceutical use
Maroua Rouabah, Claude Bernard University Lyon 1, France

10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20

10:25 - The Comparison of Permeability Efficacy of
10:40 Olmesartan Medoxomil Lipid Based Drug
Delivery System and Olmesartan Medoxomil
Suspension Formulations by Using Optimized
HDM-PAMPA Model
Yelda Komesli, University of Altinbas, Turkey

10:40 - Insight into amorphous solid dispersion
10:55 dissolution behaviour: laser-diffraction and Raman
spectroscopy holding hands
Maria Paisana, Hovione FarmaCiencia, Lisbon, Portugal

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 APGI award session

Maurice-Marie Janot Award: Robert Langer
APGI Young Investigator Award: Raul Diaz Salmeron
JDDST Best Paper 2020 Award

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Juergen Siepmann, University of Lille

12:15 - Advances in nanotechnology
13:15 Patrick Couvreur, Faculty of Pharmaceutical
Sciences, Paris Sud University, France

13:15 - 14:45 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: What's new in nanotechnology? incl. Q&A

Chairs: Elias Fattal, University Paris Sud and Heike Bunjes, University of Braunschweig

14:45 - What's needed in nanomedicine?
15:30 Twan Lammers, Department Nanomedicines and
Theranostics, RWTH, Aachen University, Germany

15:35 - Nanotechnologies for advanced imaging
16:20 Nathalie Mignet, Chemical and Biological
Technologies for Health, Université de Paris,
France

16:25 - Hyperloaded polymeric micelles for chemo- and
17:10 immunotherapy
Alexander Kabanov, Eshelman School of Pharmacy
at Chapel Hill, University of North Carolina, USA

Invited talks: 3D-printing incl. Q&A

Chairs: Alvaro Goyanes, FabRx and Julian Quodbach, University of Düsseldorf

14:45 - 3D-printing of medicines and implants:
15:30 making the formulations work
Clive Roberts, School of Pharmacy, University of
Nottingham, United Kingdom

15:35 - Thermoplastic copolyesters: A promising
15:50 3D-printing excipient for personalized vaginal
inserts
Martin Spoerk, RCPE, Graz, Austria

15:50 - Semi-Solid Extrusion 3D Printing of
16:05 Orodispersible Films for Veterinary Use
Erica Sjöholm, Abo Academi University, Finland

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20 from the two short talks

16:25 - 3D-printing in an industrial GMP setting
17:10 Jaedeok Yoo, Aprelia Pharmaceuticals, Blue Ash,
OH, USA

Short talks: Pulmonary, nasal and buccal delivery

Chairs: Ajit Narang, Genetech and Johannes Bartholomäus, PharmaKreativ

14:45 - High potency, brittle matrix tacrolimus powders
15:00 for dry powder for inhalation by thin film freezing
Sawitree Sahakijpijarn, University of Texas at
Austin, USA

15:00 - Delivery of beclomethasone dipropionate
15:15 nanosuspensions via electronic cigarette
Luca Casula, University of Cagliari, Italy

15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30

15:35 - P. aeruginosa biofilm infected bronchial
15:50 epithelium as test-system for anti-infective
aerosol formulations
Claus-Michael Lehr, Saarland University,
Saarbrücken, Germany

15:50 - Evaluation of a novel probiotic nasal spray in
16:05 human volunteers
Filip Kiekens, University of Antwerp, Belgium

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20

16:25 - Nanofibers with antibiotics and probiotics for the
16:40 two-stage therapy of periodontal disease
Spela Zupancic, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

16:40 - Mucoadhesive films to elicit nanoparticle buccal
16:55 permeation
Javier Morales, University de Chile, Santiago, Chile

Programme

16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Short talks: Tablets and coated tablets

Chairs: Kathrin Bartscher, NextPharma and Rok Dreu, University of Ljubljana

- 14:45 - Profiling the influence of process parameters on the interfacial properties of bilayer tablets
15:00 Jan Hendrik Finke, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany
- 15:00 - Evaluation of the performance of an external lubrication system implemented in a compaction simulator
15:15 Cedrine de Backere, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Influence of the unloading conditions on capping and lamination during tableting: numerical and experimental study
15:50 Vincent Mazel, University of Bordeaux, France
- 15:50 - Development of Mini-Tablets with SSR-25
16:05 Valentine Elezaj, University of Düsseldorf, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - High solids film coating systems: continuous vs. batch processing
16:40 Christian Mühlenfeld, Ashland Industries Deutschland GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany
- 16:40 - Effect of the compaction parameters on the final structure and properties of a press-coated tablet (Tab-in-Tab): experimental and numerical study of the influence of core and shell dimensions
16:55 Léo Picart, University of Bordeaux, France
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Thursday, 13 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session			
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch			
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: Formulation issues for biotech drugs incl. Q&A

Chairs: Chris van der Walle, GSK and Karoline Bechtold-Peters, Novartis

08:45 - Pellet freeze-drying of biopharmaceuticals
09:30 Stefan Schneid, Bayer, Wuppertal, Germany

- 09:35 - Please stay my dear: Interfacial adsorption as driving force for protein particle formation during peristaltic pumping
09:50 Natalie Deiringer, University of Munich, Germany
- 09:50 - Creating Highest Quality L yophilisates With Low Oxygen and Water Content by Smart Polymer Packaging
10:05 Nicole Hårdter, University of Munich, Germany
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Biologics drug product development: challenges at the interface of formulation, primary packaging and application
11:10 Susanne Jörg, Lonza AG, Basel, Switzerland

Invited talks: Localised drug delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Carmen Alvarez Lorenzo, University of Santiago de Compostella and Jean Christophe Leroux, ETH Zürich

- 08:45 - Jumping to the brain: tailored nanomedicines
09:30 Giovanni Tosi, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- 09:35 - Development of a dissolution method for dosage forms administered into subtenon space
09:50 Tobias Auel, University of Greifswald, Germany
- 09:50 - Impact of the in vitro release set-up on drug release from PLGA implants
10:05 Celine Bassand, University of Lille, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Inhaled chemotherapy: a new modality for lung cancer treatment?
11:10 Nathalie Wauthoz, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium

Short talks: Nanotechnology

Chairs: Guiseppe De Rosa, University of Naples and Niklas Sandler, Nanoform

- 08:45 - Heterotelechelic polymer prodrug nanoparticles for imaging and combination therapy
09:00 Julien Nicolas, University Paris-Sud, France
- 09:00 - Comparison of Exosome Loading Methodologies – Development of Blood-Brain Barrier-Targeting Exosomes via Dual Asymmetric Centrifugation
09:15 Anne Mahringer, University of Heidelberg, Germany
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Antiangiogenic folate-targeted nanoparticles for docetaxel delivery in ovarian cancer
09:50 Claudia Conte, University of Naples Federico II, Italy
- 09:50 - Cellular and subcellular targeting of TRAP1 as a new therapeutic approach for cancer treatment
10:05 Clelia Mathieu, Institute Galien - Paris Sud, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - Effects of cytokines release in tissue regeneration and cancer treatments
10:40 Slivia Pisani, University of Pavia, Italy
- 10:40 - Bacterial membrane vesicles as novel treatment avenue for intracellular infections
10:55 Gregor Fuhrmann, HIPS, Saarbrücken, Germany

Programme

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Short talks: Continuous manufacturing / Modeling and simulation

Chairs: Joao Pinto, University of Lisbon and Martin Bornhöft, APV

08:45 - Characterization of a Continuous Small-Scale Solid-Liquid Separator for Filtration, Washing, and Drying of Pharmaceutical Suspensions
09:00
Claas Steenweg, University of Dortmund, Germany

09:00 - Continuous production of cyclodextrin-based reconstitution powder from aqueous solution using scaled-up electrospinning
09:15
Panna Vass, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary

09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30

09:35 - An in-silico workflow for designing a continuous mixing process with DEM simulations
09:50
Peter Toson, RCPE, Graz, Austria

09:50 - Visualization of solvent effects on crystal surfaces by chemical force mapping - a combined experimental and simulation approach
10:05
Mikkel Herzberg, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20

10:25 - Predicting crystal breakage in pharmaceutical agitated dryers
10:40
Francois Hallac, University of Leeds, UK

10:40 - Dissolution and re-crystallization of supersaturated indomethacin solutions
10:55
Andreas Danzer, University of Dortmund, Germany

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 APV award session

APV Research Award 2019/2020: Olivia Merkel
APB Best Thesis Award 2019/2020: Flavia Fontana
EJPB Best Paper Award 2020

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Joerg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf

12:15 - Pharmacomicrobiomics: drugs meet the human microbiome
13:15
Christine Moissl-Eichinger, Medical University of Graz, Austria

13:15 - 14:45 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: Oral drug delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Robert O. Williams, University of Texas and Joerg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf

14:45 - Hydrophobic ion pairs: A game-changing approach for delivery of BCS class 3 drugs
15:30
Andreas Bernkop-Schnürch, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, University of Innsbruck, Austria

15:35 - Biological barriers to oral delivery of macromolecules
16:20
Caitriona O'Driscoll, School of Pharmacy, University of Cork, Ireland

16:25 - The virtual patient and the in-silico design of solid dosage forms
17:10
Hans Leuenberger, College of Pharmacy, University of Florida, Lake Nona Medical Campus, Orlando, FL, USA

Invited talks: Amorphous drug delivery systems incl. Q&A

Chairs: Susanne Page, Roche and Thomas Rades, University of Copenhagen

14:45 - Hybrid mixtures: A perspective on amorphous solid dispersions in food applications
15:30
Lennart Fries, Nestlé Research Center, Vevey, Switzerland

15:35 - Rational selection of Amorphous Solid Dispersion (ASD) Compositions for Improving Drug Candidate Bio-performance
16:20
David Lyon, Lonza, USA

16:25 - Talk to be determined
17:10
Speaker tbc

Short talks: 2D- and 3D-printing

Chairs: Milen Dimitrov, University of Sofia and Natalja Genina, University of Copenhagen

14:45 - Direct powder extrusion 3D-printing: novel technology for manufacturing amorphous solid dispersions
15:00
Alvaro Goyanes, FabRx, London, UK

15:00 - Semi-solid extrusion and alginate ionotropic gelation: a successful duo for the production of personalized floating formulations via 3D printing
15:15
Paola Russo, University of Salerno, Fisciano, Italy

15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30

15:35 - Selective laser sintering of solid oral dosage forms with copovidone and paracetamol using a CO₂ laser
15:50
Yanis Abdelhamid Gueche, University of Montpellier, France

15:50 - Direct-ink writing of implantable hybrid PCL/PEO drug delivery systems
16:05
Se Hun Chung, University College London, UK

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20

16:25 - Investigations on inkjet printed metoprolol tartrate orodispersible films for paediatric application
16:40
Olga Kiefer, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

16:40 - Traceable personalized oral dosage forms containing cannabinoids
16:55
Natalja Genina, University of Copenhagen, Finland

16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Programme

Short talks: Skin delivery and protein formulations

Chairs: Nina Dragicevic, Singidenum University and Majella Lane, University College London

- 14:45 - A new approach to predict in vitro-in vivo correlation for transdermal therapeutic systems
15:00 René Rietscher, LTS Lohmann Therapie-Systeme, Andernach, Germany
- 15:00 - Proliposomes for the production of deformable liposomes containing drug micelles
15:15 Silvia Franze, Univeristy of Milan, Italy
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - EPR study of effect of ascorbic acid on hair and feather samples in relation to eumelanins and pheomelanins
15:50 Michael Lawson, University of Bratislava, Slovakia
- 15:50 - α -relaxation studies to improve long term stability of lyophilized products from a thermodynamical point of view
16:05 Sebastial Groel, Univeristy of Munich, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Continuous alternative to freeze-drying: solid formulation of a monoclonal antibody using high-speed electrospinning
16:40 Júlia Domján, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary
- 16:40 - A holistic approach to develop a spray-drying method for CXCL8
16:55 Sonja Hartl, RCPE, Graz, Austria
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

- 09:35 - Digital Process Design
10:20 Sean Bermingham, Process System Enterprise (PSE), London, United Kingdom
- 10:25 - Study of the drying process in simulated pharmaceutical coatings: Model and experiment
10:40 Ondrej Navratil, University of Prague, Czech Republic
- 10:40 - In silico design of tablet microstructure by evolutionary algorithm
10:55 Frantisek Stepanek, University of Prague, Czech Republik
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10 from the two short talks

Invited talks: Nanofabrication technologies incl. Q&A

Chairs: Claus-Michael Lehr, University of Saarbrücken and Maria Carafa, University of Rome

- 08:45 - Novel manufacturing for healthcare: microbubbles, particles, capsules and fibres
09:30 Mohan Edirisinghe, Biomaterials Processing Laboratory, Department Mechanical Engineering, University College London, United Kingdom
- 09:35 - Advances in electrospinning
10:20 Nalin de Silva, Department of Chemistry, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka
- 10:25 - Advanced in vitro lung-on-chip platforms for inhalation assays
11:10 Josue Sznitman, Department of Biomedical Engineering, Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel

Short talks: Gene delivery and ATMP

Chairs: Nathalie Mignet, University Paris Descards and Juan M. Irache, University of Navarra

- 08:45 - Formulation development to stabilize viral vectors
09:00 Julia Rabas, Leukocare, Munich, Germany
- 09:00 - Tablets of siRNA lipoplexes: impact of processes on structure and gene-silencing efficacy
09:15 Virgine Busignies, University of Bordeaux, France
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Anti-EGFR nanovector of siRNA - a theranostic tool for triple negative breast cancer active targeting
09:50 Phuoc Vinh Nguyen, Tours University, France
- 09:50 - siRNA in lung slices: knocking down fibrosis?
10:05 Mitchel Ruigrok, University of Groningen, The Netherlands
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - mRNA based Skin Vaccination by intradermal application of lipid coated polymeric nanoparticles
10:40 Lena Kliesch, Helmholtz-Institute for Pharmaceutical Research Saarland, Germany
- 10:40 - MSC extracellular vesicles for treatment of alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency pulmonary diseases
10:55 Elia Bari, University of Pavia, Italy
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Friday, 14 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session			
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch			
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: In silico simulation for manufacturing processes incl. Q&A

Chairs: Pierre Tchoreloff, University of Bordeaux and Peter Kleinebudde, University of Düsseldorf

- 08:45 - Digitalization in pharmaceutical product and process design: from advanced simulations to virtual drug product development
09:30 Johannes Khinast, Graz University of Technology, Austria

Programme

Short talks: Advanced drug delivery

Chairs: Olivia Merkel, University of Munich and Hendrik von Büren, AbbVie

- 08:45 - Repurposing of cationic amphiphiles to promote cytosolic RNA delivery
09:00 Koen Raemdonck, Ghent University, Belgium
- 09:00 - Alginate-spermidine microgels as filling matrix of multi-channel PLGA scaffolds for the treatment of peripheral nerve injuries
09:15 Caterina Valentino, University of Pavia, Italy
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Preparation and evaluation of anticancer agent nanocrystals
09:50 Yohann Corvis, University of Paris, France
- 09:50 - Evaluation of in vivo efficacy of ferrocifen loaded lipid nanocapsules on ovarian cancer
10:05 Elise Lepeltier, University of Angers, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - A novel polyethylene glycol-based linker platform for the development of hydrophilic antibody-drug conjugates
10:40 Tommaso Tedeschini, University of Padova, Italy
- 10:40 - Dithiolane-crosslinked polymer micelles: reduction responsive drug release
10:55 Cornelus van Nostrum, University of Utrecht, The Netherlands
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 International ADRITELF Award 2020

Giuseppe De Rosa, University of Naples Federico II, Italy
Chair: Anna-Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari and Paolo Caliceti, University of Padova

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Anna-Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari and Paolo Caliceti, University of Padova

- 12:15 - Oral drug delivery systems: from irrelevance to top-selling products and ongoing challenges
13:15 Andrea Gazzaniga, Biopharmaceuticals and Pharmaceutical Technology Laboratory, University of Milan, Italy

13:00 - 15:00 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: Dermal and transdermal delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Paola Minghetti, University of Milan and Dominique Lunter, University of Tuebingen

- 14:45 - Skin permeation from Pickering emulsions
15:30 Marie-Alexandrine Bolzinger, Claude Bernard University Lyon, France
- 15:35 - Microarray patches for high-dose drug delivery: targeting global healthcare challenges
16:20 Ryan F. Donnelly, School of Pharmacy, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom

- 16:25 - Improved vaccine immunogenicity through microneedle delivery
17:10 Michael Schrader, Vaxess, Boston, MA, USA

Invited talks: Continuous manufacturing incl. Q&A

Chairs: Ali Rajabi-Siahboomi, Colorcon and Michael Repka, University of Mississippi

- 14:45 - Process development of the future: fully automated DoE process analysis in an integrated continuous manufacturing plant for solid oral dosage forms
15:30 Victoria Pauli, Novartis, Basel, Switzerland
- 15:35 - Residence Time Distribution (RTD) concept as element in drug product quality control strategies for continuous manufacturing
16:20 Bart Nitert, Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Beerse, Belgium
- 16:25 - Continuous manufacturing of solid dosage forms; opportunities and controversies
17:10 Kendal Pitt, GlaxoSmithKline, Ware, United Kingdom

Short talks: Oral drug delivery / Pediatric formulations

Chairs: Sandra Klein, University of Greifswald and Luigi Boltri, Adare

- 14:45 - The Use of Partially Hydrolysed Polyvinyl Alcohol for The Production of High Drug-Loaded Sustained Release Pellets via Extrusion-Spheronization and Coating: In Vitro and In Vivo Evaluation
15:00 Valerie Vanhoome, University of Ghent, Belgium
- 15:00 - X-ray imaging of microrcontainers used for oral drug delivery
15:15 Rolf B. Kjeldsen, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Controlled permeability enhancement with short peptide inhibitors of protein kinase C zeta
15:50 Joel Brunner, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 15:50 - A toolbox for mimicking gastrointestinal conditions in children: S(imulated) P(aediatric) B(reakfast) M(edia) for addressing the variability of gastric contents after typical paediatric breakfasts
16:05 Lisa Freerks, University of Greifswald, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Design and evaluation of self-emulsifying drug delivery system for pediatric use
16:40 Xiaona Liu, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- 16:40 - Acceptability of antibiotics in pediatrics: findings from an international observational study
16:55 Thibault Vallet, ClinSearch, Malakoff, France
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Short talks: Processing and PAT

Chairs: Javier O. Morales, University of Chile and Francisco Otero Espinar, University of Santiago de Compostella

- 14:45 - Improving flowability and reducing storage agglomeration of metformin hydrochloride through QESD crystallization
15:00 Jerome Hansen, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

Programme

- 15:00 - Production and downstream-processing of API-nanosuspensions
15:15 Arno Kwade, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Improving particle size distributions in a conical mill through new impeller air flow optimization comparisons utilizing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis and empirical DoE
15:50 Wilf Sanguesa, Quadro Engineering, Ontario, Canada
- 15:50 - Innovative preparation of API salt coated on particles using fluidised bed
16:05 Jakub Muzik, University of Prague, Czech Republik
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Insight into the impact of compaction process variations on tablet disintegration by non-destructive at-line terahertz porosity sensing
16:40 Prince Bawuah, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
- 16:40 - NIR as an in-line PAT tool to study desorption kinetics in spin freeze-dried formulations
16:55 Laurens Leys, Ghent University, Belgium
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10
- 17:15 End of conference

Poster sessions

Wednesday, 12 May 2021

Nanoparticles and vesicles
Dermal preparations
Transdermal delivery
Protein formulation and aggregation
Gene delivery
Cellular drug transport
Parenteral delivery
Quality control and PAT
Quality assurance
Green and sustainable pharma

Thursday, 13 May 2021

Oral delivery
Controlled drug delivery
Advanced drug delivery systems
Advance therapy medicinal products
Technical innovations
Pediatric and geriatric drug delivery
Veterinary medicine
Packaging
Regulatory affairs

Friday, 14 May 2021

Pharmaceutical manufacturing and engineering
Bioavailability and absorption enhancement
In-vitro/In-vivo correlations
Stability testing
Preformulation
Physical pharmacy
Starting materials
Pulmonary delivery
Buccal and nasal delivery

Chairs and committees

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Eva Roblegg, University of Vienna/University of Graz, Austria

Co-chairs of the conference

Jörg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf, Germany
Anna Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari, Italy
Jürgen Siepmann, University of Lille, France

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